

The Number Six as a Cultural Marker in Ao Naga Traditional Society

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Abstract

The Ao Naga tribe inhabits Mokokchung district in Nagaland, a state situated in the northeastern region of India. Various cultures worldwide assign numbers with a certain significance based on factors such as mythology, cosmology, or utility, within their own cultural context. The number six, known as terok in Ao language, had high cultural value in the traditional Ao Naga society. The Ao Nagas had a religion known as Limapur prior to their acceptance of Christianity. Their origin myth known as Lungterok (six stones) myth, and the counting system, also reflects the importance of six in their culture. They practiced a rare system of overcounting cardinal number system where a distinct change in the counting pattern or structure emphasized the importance of six. Performing numerous rites and rituals was necessary for the Ao in their indigenous religion, and the idea of six being the perfect or complete number was central to these performances. Six pervaded the Ao universe, and it was a cultural marker and an essential part of their customs, rituals and beliefs. Ao Naga customs and beliefs are well documented in the works of Christian missionaries and British colonial administrators from the nineteenth century. Indigenous writers from the tribe have also made significant contributions to the study of the tribe. Numerous references to the use of six in rites and rituals have been made in these works, but the significance of six as a cultural marker has not been examined. Synthesizing data from these sources and examining the cultural significance of six can help gain fresh perspectives on the Ao Naga society.

Keywords: Ao Naga, six, cultural marker, complete number, origin myth.

The Number Six as a Cultural Marker in Ao Naga Traditional Society Mokokchung district in Nagaland, a state located in northeast of India, is home to the Ao Nagas. The traditional Ao Naga religion before the advent of Christianity and British colonial power in their territory, was known as *Limapur*. This religion was marked by many rites and rituals and ceremonies offered to many gods and spirits. The significance of six was evident in the structuring of their rites and rituals around the number, with rituals lasting for six days or performed in the sixth month or the sixth year. Under the Ao Naga traditional system of counting, numeric quantities were communicated verbally. They practiced a rare system of overcounting cardinal number system where a distinct change in the counting pattern or structure occurred at numbers associated with six, like 16, 26, 36 and so on, emphasizing the importance of six even in their

counting. The *Lungterok* myth, which describes their origin, mentions that they originated from six stones. The use of six to represent or restore balance and completeness pervaded the Ao universe. Its central role in the social, cultural and religious life of the Aos makes it an essential component of Ao cultural identity. The study of Ao Naga society would not be complete without mentioning six as a cultural marker.

The nineteenth century writings of Christian missionaries and administrators of the British colonial power, offer a wealth of information about the practices, traditions, and beliefs of the Ao Naga society. Their materials are still a valuable source of data on the tribe. The use of “six” in Ao customs and traditions is referenced in numerous reports in these writings but not examined in depth. Although the tribe’s indigenous writers have significantly advanced our understanding of the Ao society, the importance of “six” as a cultural marker has not yet received enough attention. The purpose of this paper is to synthesize information from these sources and gain new insights or understanding about the Ao Naga society. The potential of such a study to deepen and broaden our understanding of traditional Ao society makes it valuable even though the number’s historical importance as a cultural marker is no longer relevant or applicable in the contemporary Christian Ao society.

In the Ao universe, six had a symbolic significance that transcended its numerical value. It was connected to their origin myth known as *Lungterok* myth. The term *Lungterok* is a compound word derived from the two words *lung* and *terok*. In the Ao language, the translation for *lung* is stone and *terok* is six. Traditional Ao beliefs hold that they originated from these six stones. It is believed that the stones, three for each gender, represent the male and female reproductive organs.

Their customs, rituals and ceremonies reflected the significance of number six. They engaged in numerous rituals and ceremonies that were believed to bring about balance and harmony in their universe. Their belief was that these practices would ward off evil, cleanse themselves of evil, and ensure the well-being of the community. Almost all of these occasions required observing seclusion and abstinence. Sexual and dietary abstinence was the primary forms of abstinence. The Ao language referred to this observance of seclusion and abstinence as *Among*. Jamir (2012) mentions that depending on the occasion, an individual, group of people, or the entire village could observe *Among*, and it was rigorously implemented (160). There were several *Amongs* which required six days abstinence.

According to Ao (2017), *Menen Mong* was the abstinence performed in the event of an unnatural death (p. 69). Ao (2017) further explained that deaths resulting from falling off a tree, a high cliff, or from wild animals, as well as death of a woman during childbirth and suicides were considered unnatural deaths (p. 69). Smith (1925) wrote that the purification process was initiated due to the belief that some deity was angry and had cursed the individual (p. 105).

Among was observed by the whole village for six days in such cases. Jamir (2012) explained that the villagers stayed inside their homes and abstained from going to the fields,

constructing houses or performing any manual labour (p. 161). Jamir (2012) further elaborated on the ritual process that while the entire village observed *among* for six days, the family of the deceased was temporarily ostracized from the village for a month right after the completion of the six days' seclusion. They receive food from the clan priest prepared by their clan members during their six-day stay indoors. The clan priest leaves the provisions outside the house without speaking to them. When leaving their house, everything must be destroyed, including their clothes. The clan members help them out by donating some clothes and a temporary dwelling is constructed with leaves for them outside the village where they live out their thirty days. When the specified period of time is over, they reenter the community and must begin anew with a new house with new possessions. When a woman died in childbirth, the community observed *Among* for three days only, but the family of the deceased had to observe the full period just like in other situations classified as unnatural deaths (161, 162).

It was believed that by observing *Among*, the gods would be appeased and the curse associated with the circumstances of unnatural death would cease. The ritual's effectiveness was dependent on completing the six-day period and it was rigorously enforced. In cases where the death was believed to be normal, the mourning period observed for men was six days and for women it was five days. The tribe continues to observe the mourning period even though they have been practicing Christianity for decades. The Ao Senden, the governing body of the Ao tribe, has reduced the mourning period down to three days.

According to Jamir (2012), birth ceremony of both male and female children involved naming and ear-piercing ceremonies (p. 108). Their pierced ears were ornamented with red hairs and black feathers taken from the Malayan wreathed Hornbill. Ao (2012) notes that this ceremony happened in the sixth month after the child's birth (p. 52). Jamir (2012) further stated that the number of feathers that adorned the child's ears was determined by their gender. If the child was male, the tuft of feathers was six, whereas it was five for females (108).

Ao (2017) commented on the Ao tribe's belief that the pierced ears represented a symbolic purpose beyond mere ornamentation. It denoted the child as belonging to the societal category of "man" (p. 52). Further, six feathers on a child's ears represented their masculine gender classification because six was associated with men according to Ao beliefs and practices. In the same way, a female child had five feathers on her ears to identify her as a female. The assigning of "six" and "five" as male and female numbers is rooted in the Ao belief that a man has six spirits and a woman has five spirits. Jamir (2012) stated that the AOs held the belief that human beings have multiple spirits. They believed that men had six spirits and women possessed five spirits (p. 124). The use of "five" as a gender symbol was restricted to birth and death ceremonies of women, but six was considered the complete number and utilized for all other purposes.

Six was also incorporated in marriage ceremonies of the AOs. According to Ao (2017) two of the groom's friends were required to provide six pot-stands for holding cooking pots and six bamboo cylinders for storing water, to be used during the feast. It was part of the ritual

(p. 50). The use of the number six was an important element even in the construction of important places. The *Ariju* which was a socio-political institution for the training of the young and also served as a military fort was rebuilt every six years. Mills (1926) reported that the ceremonies entailed the old men of the clan invoking blessings for the *Arju* to thrive and produce many wise men. Following the ceremony, they were given a portion of ceremonial meat and were then required to observe seclusion and abstinence for six days (p. 75). Jamir (2017) also stated the existence of a similar practice while setting up a new log drum in the village. The log drum or *sungkong* was found in every Ao village. Different types of beats were utilized to communicate important or urgent information to the community using the log drum. This log measuring thirty to forty feet long was an object of worship and its installation involved elaborate ceremonies. Jamir (2012) further stated that the *Tir* or the religious head of the *Arichu* was required to observe seclusion and abstinence for six days on completing the rites and rituals (p. 37). Even their festivals were governed by the six-day rule. The most important festival of the Ao Nagas was *Moatsu*. It was a harvest festival during which they expressed gratitude to the gods for the abundant harvest, the land and the natural world. Jamir (2017) wrote that *Moatsu* was celebrated for six days (p. 80). Regarding rituals and sacrifices, Smith (1925) noted,

In all these sacrifices, six seems to be the perfect number. They put six pieces of liver, six pieces of meat and the like into each of the small bundles, while the packages go in multiples of sixes; that is, thirty, sixty, one hundred and twenty, etc. (p. 86).

The Aos were involved in the practice of headhunting. It involved bringing the opponents' heads to the village and hanging it on a tree called the head tree. According to Jamir (2012), the *Tir* or religious head carried out a rite of retribution soon after the war party arrived. The *Tir* would declare that that heads were taken only as a punishment for the wrongs committed by the victim or the victim's community. On the sixth day after the ritual, the heads were hung on the head tree (p. 58). The sixth day was considered an auspicious day representing the restoration of balance in their world through revenge. It represented completion of the task of restoration.

Under the Ao Naga oral culture, numerical concepts were conveyed orally. The incredibly rare overcounting system was used by the Aos for mathematical operations. An article titled "Overcounting Numeral Systems and Their Relevance to Sub-grouping in the Tibeto-Burman languages of Nagaland" noted that "Overcounting systems are extremely rare typologically and have only been reported in a handful of languages spoken in a few areas of the world" (Coupe, 2012, p. 205). According to Mazaudon (1969), "(Menninger, Number Words and Number Symbols; A Cultural History of Numbers, 1969) (1969) recorded that overcounting system 'has been reported from two areas of the globe: the Germanic North of Europe and Central America'" (as cited in Mazaudon, 2008, p. 4).

Names for numbers up to a thousand and mathematical operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and fractions were referred to as *Ongko* in the Ao language. Their system of overcounting cardinal numbers involved a distinct modification in the counting pattern or structure for numbers associated with six, like 16, 26, 36, and so on. According to

Clark (1893), in the Ao numerical concept, compounds were formed up to fifteen. According to Avery (1886), compound phrases from eleven to fifteen are created by arranging the smaller number after the bigger one, without the use of a connective (p. 45). For e.g., *teri-ka* means ‘ten-one,’ *teri-asem* means ‘ten-three,’ and *teri-pungu* means ‘ten-five’ (p. 351). At sixteen, the overcounting pattern commences by employing a negated verb stem like “not brought.” Clark (1893) recorded the following:

But when the six is reached in the compounds, the succeeding ten seems to be anticipated, and we have for sixteen ‘metsy maben trok’ twenty not brought six, equivalent to the sixteen before twenty; ‘metsv; maben tenet, the seventeen before twenty, &c. In the same manner from twenty-six to thirty, on reaching the six, thirty is anticipated, thus ‘semyr maben trok’ the six before thirty, “twenty-six, ‘lir maben trok’ the six before forty, thirty-six, &c (p. 45).

The Aos speak two major languages, namely Chungli and Mongsen. According to Coupe’s (2012) research, *myuki mepen terok*, which translates to “(the) twenty not completed (the) six” is how the Mongsen Ao language expresses sixteen (p. 206). The counting in tens also reflects a change in pattern after reaching sixty or *rokyr* in the Ao language. Seventy was referred to as fifty and twenty, eighty as twice forty and so on. Compared to other numeral systems, overcounting systems are rare and poorly documented, which makes it difficult to comprehend or interpret. According to Claude (2012), “. . . number words constitute a tool that is heavily dependent upon the cultural context of the speakers whose language they inhabit, on the value that such speakers attach to them, and on the quantic needs they have. . .” (p. 4). In the traditional Ao universe, six was more than just a numerical value. It held symbolic and cultural meaning.

The Aos clearly prioritized six and prominently featured it in important rituals and ceremonies. It was considered as the perfect and complete number. Furthermore, their cultural belief surrounding six was intimately linked to their counting system, shaping their understanding of the world. The significance of six as a cultural marker was strengthened by its integration into their everyday lives. Analyzing the significance of six in Ao culture can give us insight into how numbers, beliefs, and cultural practices combine to shape various other human communities.

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